

IMPORTANCE OF NATIONAL IDEALS AND SPIRITUALITY IN RAISING YOUNG PEOPLE AS COMPLETE HUMAN BEINGS

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Abstract: This study provides information about the role of the national idea in the education of youth, the importance of spirituality in raising young people as complete individuals. During the study, it was found that instilling spiritual values in the lives of young people increases their social responsibility, increases their interest in learning, and serves to educate them in the spirit of patriotism. It also provides information about the opportunities that are being created for our youth today and the attention paid to their education.

Keywords: National idea, spirituality, perfect person, upbringing, worldview, spiritual consciousness, education, perfect person, national values.

Introduction

In today's era of globalization, the national idea and spirituality play a decisive role in the education of youth. In the current conditions, when economic, political and cultural ties between the peoples of the world are increasingly strengthened, an idea that unites the nation, preserves its identity, history, culture and values, is necessary. In this sense, the national idea is an important source for the formation of noble feelings such as patriotism, dedication, hard work, and humanity in the heart and spiritual consciousness of every person. The young generation is the future of any society, the force that ensures its development. Therefore, educating youth in the spirit of the national idea and spirituality is one of the priority areas of state policy. By educating spiritually mature, self-confident, and patriotic youth, stability and development in society can be achieved. The issue of national identity and spirituality is closely related to the traditions, values, customs, and religious beliefs of the Uzbek people, which have been formed over the centuries. In order to fully satisfy the spiritual needs of young people, it is necessary to raise the important means of education to a new qualitative level. At the same time, it is necessary to quickly eliminate the existing major and minor shortcomings and shortcomings in these areas, to get rid of such negative situations. The importance of philosophical, socio-political and humanitarian sciences in the spiritual and moral education of young people in our country is incomparable, therefore, it is necessary for representatives of these sciences to fulfill the extremely responsible tasks set for themselves at the level

of today's requirements. The level of textbooks, manuals, literature and specialists in this regard is also required to be high. From the above, we can conclude that our people, first of all, need to be constantly alert, vigilant and vigilant, to conduct deeply thought-out, scientifically based and continuous spiritual education against threats. Therefore, the deep inculcation of the national idea and spirituality in the education of youth, their implementation in life is becoming an urgent issue. The national idea is the historical memory of the people, its goals and aspirations, a common ideological direction for survival and development as a people. It is recognized as a factor that unites society, providing it with a spiritual and moral foundation. In the case of Uzbekistan, this idea found its expression in the aspiration of our people for independence, freedom, patriotism, and justice. The national idea is the force that mobilizes the nation towards a single goal. It encourages the people to understand their identity, appreciate their history, and preserve their national values. In this regard, the national idea forms a positive worldview, patriotism, faith, and pride in the minds of young people. Spirituality is a person's inner world, his beliefs, values, ethics, culture, and worldview. A spiritually mature person is one who respects himself, society, and those around him, and strives for goodness. Therefore, strengthening spirituality is the basis for raising young people as well-rounded individuals. Spirituality teaches a person to understand his place in society, to feel his duty and responsibility. The role of the family, educational institutions, cultural centers, mass media, religious and social institutions in this process is incomparable. The national idea and spirituality are complementary concepts. Without spiritually rich people, the national idea cannot exist, and without the national idea, spirituality cannot develop. As a result of their harmony, feelings of social cohesion, civic responsibility, and awareness of national identity are formed in society. If the national idea is the leading force of spirituality, spirituality is the vital basis of the national idea, a means of instilling it in the human heart. Therefore, these two concepts must be implemented in a harmonious manner in the education of young people. The spiritual values of the Uzbek people are a rich heritage that has been formed over the centuries, uniting society and calling people to goodness. These are expressed in qualities such as hard work, respect for elders, kindness to younger ones, honesty, justice, patience, honor, and patriotism. As young people assimilate these values, they strive for spiritual maturity as individuals. Especially in today's era, when the flow of information has increased and various foreign ideas are entering, relying on national values equips young people with ideological immunity. It is known that

in the present era, the process of globalization is rapidly and deeply penetrating our lives. Globalization is, first of all, the process of an unprecedented acceleration of the pace of life, the strengthening of various integration and cooperation between countries, the rapid spread of modern information technologies and scientific achievements, the acquisition of a new quality of dialogue between peoples, the emergence of opportunities for mutual cooperation - this is the positive significance of globalization, but another aspect of the globalization process today is that it is becoming a tool for ideological influence on young people, a stage for the struggle of various political and ideological forces. For this reason, the education of youth has always been in the focus of attention of our state, and this process has been continuing continuously during the years of independence. In general, all laws on youth adopted in our country serve to comprehensively educate our youth, as well as to ensure their activity and participation in the international arena, to provide socio-economic protection for minors, orphans, and large families, and to identify and support talented youth. It is noteworthy that in our country, special attention, love, and care are being paid to children deprived of parental love and upbringing, and to children with disabilities. The issues of gradually strengthening the material and technical base of orphanages, boarding schools, and preschool educational institutions, and radically improving the educational process have been identified. The role of the community and the general public in educating young people, who are the creators of a new society, is great. Therefore, the prosperity of our country and the well-being of our country must be able to justify the trust placed in our youth. We need to plant the seeds of knowledge in the hearts of every young person, protect them from being poisoned by those with various malicious intentions, and respond with our knowledge and thinking to those who want to deprive us of our identity and traditions, and who cannot see the peace of our country. For this purpose, great importance is attached to the proper organization and meaningful spending of young people's free time in our country, to the upbringing of patriotic and humanitarian feelings in them. Spirituality is the main factor determining the development of society, the development of the nation and the development of the individual. Through the promotion of the national idea and spirituality, young people are also given moral education. After all, moral education is one of the continuous processes that ensure the development of a person as a person. In it, a person understands moral values, stabilizes moral qualities in himself, and learns to live based on moral principles and norms. Moral education has been seeking answers to two important questions throughout human history: one of

them is how to live, the other is what to do and what not to do. The process of seeking answers to these questions is a practical expression of moral education. Moral education is one of the ways to bring a human child to perfection and perfection. It has many means. One of such means is the further improvement of national ideological education. Because only when spirituality develops can economic and socio-political stability be achieved in society, and the country and nation rise. This, in turn, serves as a necessary basis for the development and perfection of the individual.

Conclusion

The role of the national idea and spirituality in the education of youth is incomparable. After all, it is the spiritually mature, nationally proud, loyal to the values of their people, and selfless youth that are the most important support of society. The national idea and spirituality are an ideological shield that protects youth from any foreign influences. In today's era of globalization, preserving the national identity of youth, encouraging them to be kind, patriotic, and hardworking, in turn, is a guarantee of the development and stability of our country. Therefore, educating the youth of Uzbekistan in the spirit of the national idea and spirituality is the sacred duty of not only the education system, but also the entire society. The national idea is the light that unites us, and spirituality is the light that illuminates our hearts.

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